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ALEXANDER HAY

A Man of Many Depths – Hugh Miller and
The Cruise of the Betsey

Abstract

Hugh Miller was many things in his life: a geologist, a journalist, a historian and a leading figure in the establishment of the Free Church in 1843. However his work also involved the sea and maritime issues to a considerable degree; in particular, his two companion narratives, *The Cruise of the Betsey* and *Rambles of a Geologist*. These addressed the experiences of coastal and island communities, and the social and religious issues they faced, but also allowed for an exploration of Scotland's fossilised deposits and its prehistoric marine wildlife. Yet the sea also allowed Miller to explore deeper issues in regards to his background, his faith and his worldview. The oceans proved a fitting canvas for Miller's childhood traumas, in the form of his father's death at sea, in addition to his own approach to romanticism and spirituality. This paper therefore explores an often nuanced and complicated, yet vivid and inspired relationship between Miller and the seas that fascinated him.

INTRODUCTION

Hugh Miller (1802–1856) was in his time a stonemason, geologist, journalist, lay churchman, historian, social campaigner and folklorist. He was also a palaeontologist whose work on fossilised sea life was of great significance, and this was but one of many examples where he addressed the sea in his writing. To examine this aspect of his life, then, is to appreciate his work in its proper context – yet to what extent did the sea influence and resonate through it?

Miller certainly provided plentiful material on the subject; during his

time editing the *Witness* newspaper, Miller would write over ten thousand words a week¹ and such prodigious output explored the oceans in depth, amongst a myriad of other subjects. One particular example was his book, *The Cruise of the Betsey*,² published posthumously in 1858, but with content first featured in the *Witness* during June 1846. *The Cruise of the Betsey* itself covers Miller's three-week exploration of the Inner Hebrides by sea, primarily to examine its geology, but as we will discuss, it is also an exploration of its social, spiritual and social conditions and the role of the sea in all of these cases.

Equally relevant was *Rambles of a Geologist*, written in 1847, which featured Miller's geological work in other regions in Scotland, dwelling in detail on the maritime experience in these places, coastal communities and yet more examples of fossilised sea life. Fittingly then, both texts are often published in the same volume, and so this article will explore both. In addition, it will discuss other relevant texts written by Miller and demonstrate a continuity between both them and his own writing overall.

MILLER'S BACKGROUND

Miller's maritime connections extended beyond his journalism and palaeontology. Indeed, Miller's father was a sea captain, who went down on his ship, while the rest of his ancestors were sailors of one sort or another, going so far as to take part in naval battles. Of these, his grandfather and two grand uncles had also met their ends as mariners. This led to a noticeable ambivalence on Miller's part towards the sea. *The Cruise of the Betsey* has a revealing passage where a sailor laments his son's horror and grief at being offshore and away from home. Tellingly, the boy is mentioned to be 'scarce five years of age at the time' – the same age Miller lost his own father to the waves.

Can this ambivalence be seen, however, elsewhere in the text? It is in fact easy to observe a certain complexity in how the sea is portrayed – Miller is keen to emphasise the quality of his conditions, cramped though they were, on the ship and the dutifulness of its ship's captain, who doubled up as its minister on Sundays. Yet Miller's descriptions of life at sea, especially its less comfortable and even threatening elements are not only also recorded in detail but are distinguished with a brooding, gothic

quality, suggesting that Miller was not only willing to apply contemporary literary devices for his work³ but that these represented a deeper antipathy as well as fascination.

The gale, thickened with rain, came down, shrieking like a maniac, from off the peaked hills of Rum, striking away the tops of the long ridgy billows that had risen in the calm to indicate its approach, and then carrying them in sheets of spray aslant the furrowed surface, like snow drift hurried across a frozen field.

Miller was certainly aware and familiar with the literary trends of his time, and was noted for having an in-depth understanding of eighteenth-century literature, particularly its poetry.⁴ Certainly, his writing did at times reflect echoes of the darker side of Romanticism as this evocative passage demonstrates:

The hilltops were lost in cloud and storm; and ever and anon as a heavier shower came sweeping down on the wind, the intervening hollows closed up their gloomy vistas, and all was fog and rhyme to the water's edge.

Beyond these quotes, Miller goes so far as to quote Coleridge's *Rime of the Ancient Mariner* at one point, a deliberate act on his part as it not only demonstrates his influences, but also suggests a continuity in maritime literature. Certainly, in *The Cruise of the Betsey*, we can see this influence in how Miller describes the wretched sight of fisherman without a catch to show for their efforts:

There had been tolerable takes for a few nights in the neighbouring sea, but the fish had again disappeared, and the fishermen, whose worn-out tackle gave such evidence of a long continued run of ill luck, as I had learned to interpret on the east coast, looked gloomy and spiritless, and reported a deficient fishery.

It is easy to draw parallels between these hapless fishermen, 'gloomy and spiritless' and Coleridge's own sailors, trapped in becalmed seas: 'A weary time! A weary time! How glazed each weary eye.'⁵ In so doing, Miller was again using literary techniques and allusions to illustrate real life conditions,

but tellingly was doing so within a context of what I have previously termed literary 'Maritime Horror'.⁶ This was deliberate on Miller's part, his willingness to envisage his fossils in life with folkloric and traits rooted in dark romanticism suggesting a debt to the Gothic as well as the Geological tradition.⁷

Perhaps of all the extinct reptiles, the Plesiosaurus was the most extraordinary. An English geologist has described it, grotesquely enough, and yet most happily, as a snake threaded through a tortoise. And here on this very spot, must these monstrous dragons have disported and fed; here must they have raised their little reptile heads and long swan-like necks over the surface, to watch an antagonist or select a victim; here must they have warred and wedded, and pursued all the various instincts of their unknown natures. A strange story, surely, considering it is a true one!

Miller was not the first to see horror in the oceans. In his *Scenes and Legends of the North of Scotland*,⁸ published in 1835, Miller quotes Keats, whose own poetry – such as *On The Sea*⁹ – broods with implied menace and a threatening vastness, as well as a sense of wonder and fascination:

It keeps eternal whisperings around
 Desolate shores, and with its mighty swell
 Gluts twice ten thousand Caverns, till the spell
 Of Hecate leaves them their old shadowy sound.

In the same chapter, Miller refers to his birthplace of Cromarty as a town built on the ruins of an older settlement, swept away by the sea, and leaving behind only the eerie remnants of standing stones and the bones of the long-dead scattered on the beach after their graveyard was 'washed out of the surf'. Miller then notes that a perhaps apocryphal local seer, Thomas the Rhymer, had predicted that Cromarty would be destroyed twice in this fashion. In so doing, Miller implies that the sea, while it had made Cromarty in terms of its fishing and jute trade, was also the potential bringer of its destruction. He follows this with a more optimistic perspective, noting the willingness and ability of Cromarty's townsfolk to rebuild and persevere despite the destruction wrought upon them, yet this is a deliberate contrast on Miller's part: The ability of man to persevere is

required only because the natural world, and in particular the sea, makes it necessary. As Miller himself says at this point:

Man owes much of his ingenuity to his misfortunes; and who does not know that, were he less weak and less exposed as an animal, he would be less powerful as a rational creature.

This gives an insight into Miller's own motivations; he was a driven, versatile man by necessity, but it is telling that these 'misfortunes' are once again related to the sea, which had taken so much from him. Fittingly, then, *The Cruise of the Betsey* also alludes to this model of virtue through perseverance, significantly personified in chaste female form, in response to the sea and the threat it poses:

As the fitful gust struck her headlong, as if it had been some invisible missile hurled at us from off the hill-tops, she stooped her head lower and lower, like old stately Hardyknute under the blow of the 'King of Norse', till at length the lee chain plate rustled sharp through the foam; but, like a staunch Free Churchwoman, the lowlier she bent, the more steadfastly did she hold her head to the storm.

It is worth noting that this idealised version of womanhood contrasts with Miller's often ambivalent relationship with his own mother,¹⁰ who endured the death of her husband at sea and raised Miller, with help from his uncles, until he left home at the age of seventeen. In the sea, Miller saw not only the grave of his father, but an equally ghostly ideal of motherhood that he seemed to yearn for:

For Miller, the sea was an established antagonist but also a means through which one could both be improved and self-realised. As *The Cruise of the Betsey* demonstrates, the seas of the Inner Hebrides were a means through which he could explore the fear and fascination towards the sea that had followed him through his life.

MILLER THE PALAEOLOGIST

Of course, Miller's primary intention for going on the voyage was to explore the rich palaeontology of the Inner Hebridean islands – indeed the

alternative title of the book is *A Summer Ramble Among the Fossiliferous Deposits of the Hebrides*. Much of Miller's account is, as a result, a discussion of his finds and the identification thereof.

Significantly, however, there is a maritime context, with many such remains being found on shorelines and beaches. Alongside examples of fossilised pines, Miller also identifies extinct sea life, such as belemnites – an ancient form of cephalopod or squid – ammonites, aquatic reptiles such as the aforementioned Plesiosaurus and extinct lobe-finned fish such as *Osteolepis*, on islands including the Isle of Eigg, where he first documented extensive fossil deposits.¹¹

Beyond the maritime context, Miller's writing is significant in terms of how it combines both the technical and the vernacular in tone when describing these long dead, usually aquatic creatures. For example, in writing about the remains of a plesiosaur, Miller easily adopts the turn of phrase and language of taxonomy and life science used at the time:

I observed, too, in the slightly curved articulations of not a few of the vertebræ, the gentle convexity in the concave centre, which, if not peculiar to the Plesiosaurus, is at least held to distinguish it from most of its contemporaries.

Yet Miller also seamlessly introduces the rhetoric and turn of phrase of the journalist and the popular author, engaging as well as informing his reader in equal measure:

The reptile, since his deposition from the first place in the scale of creation, has sunk sadly in those parts: the ex-monarch has become a low plebeian.

This has echoes of Charles Dicken's own opening preamble in *Bleak House*, written in 1852, where he alludes to the "Megalosaurus, forty feet long or so" and how it might waddle "like an elephantine lizard up Holborn Hill". Palaeontology has always easily inserted itself into popular media, and the mid-nineteenth century was no exception. In 1842, four years before Miller's voyage, the geologist William Buckland had already first coined the term "dinosaur" while sculptures of *Iguanodon* and *Megalosaurus*, amongst other long-gone creatures, were unveiled at Crystal Palace just ten years

later. Prior to this, press and public interest in the fossil-hunting of Mary Anning¹² and Gideon Mantell¹³ had demonstrated that an interest in extinct megafauna was already firmly established in the culture of the day.

With that in mind, it is worth remembering that *Cruise of the Betsey* was not an academic text at all, though Miller wrote with a certain scholarly vigour and knowledge, but was written instead for the readers of the *Witness* newspaper. Here Miller was producing an early form of popular science, which by its very presence and later posthumous republication, suggests an appetite for such material. Miller uses wit, pathos and irony to discuss his work, as well as technical knowledge, in so doing, being part of the first generation of writers to make the prehistoric popular, and bringing with it an additional literary flair.¹⁴

How strange, that the identical sea heaving around stack and skerry in this remote corner of the Hebrides should have once been thronged by reptile shapes more strange than poet ever imagined, – dragons, gorgons and chimeras!

Yet it also demonstrates, a deep interest in the sea on Miller's part. He notes with interest that the fossilised pines he finds on the Isle of Eigg were brought up 'through Plutonic agency, from their deep-sea bottom'. This suggests an unusual juxtaposition of ideas, with Pluto, lord of the underworld where the spirits of the dead would go, and the depths of the ocean being conflated together into one metaphor. This and his interest in extinct 'monsters from the depths', certainly demonstrate an interest in the sea as infernal metaphor. Yet it is most potent as a place from whence the remains of the dead emerge or are exposed, as was the case in Cromarty. Miller was exploring the means and cause of his father's death.

Such a reading puts Miller's writing into a new light. When he discusses how the remains of belemnites are 'robust' and 'so often the sole survivor of its many contemporaries' he is as much writing in terms of sublime nature and its symbolic relevance, and of his own life experiences, as he is in terms of extinct sea-life. Miller's own interest in fossils began when he first saw them during his apprenticeship as a mason, which both provided the initial exposure and skills required to develop this interest, with him finding fossilised remains of the Devonian *Cocosteus* fish species in the red sandstone deposits near Cromarty itself. It seems in many ways that palaeon-

tology was both a result of and the means through which Miller could safely explore the great defining trauma of his childhood. As he wrote in his autobiographical work, *My Schools and Schoolmasters*, first published in 1852, this ongoing process of discovery and the sea were intricately connected from the beginning:

It was, however, not to the quarry itself that my first-found organisms belonged. There lies in the Firth beyond, an outlier of the Lias, which, like the Marcus' Cave one referred to in a preceding chapter, strews the beach with its fragments after every storm from the sea; and in a nodular mass of bluish-grey limestone derived from this subaqueous bed I laid open my first-found ammonite.¹⁵

Miller himself was only too aware of the metaphorical underpinnings of his work; as he also added in the same text, the fossils of ancient seas as well as those of dry land provided him a vent for his own primordial crisis and the rigours of reaching manhood in the wake of this:

How vividly the past rose up before me! – boyish day-dreams, forgotten for twenty years – the fossils of an early formation of mind, produced at a period when the atmosphere of feeling was warmer than now, and the immaturities of the mental kingdom grew rank and large, like the ancient cryptogamia, and bore no specific resemblance to the productions of a riper time.

In so doing, Miller did not wallow in despair or obsession, but rather, used his personal tragedy as a foundation to build something both rewarding and revelatory. In that way, he too was like the people of Cromarty, constructing a new beginning in the wake of seaborne disaster. For Miller, palaeontology was intermingled with the sea and its darkness, but was also a means of discovery, of the self, the wider world and the oceans. As he has been quoted, “Life is itself a school, and Nature always a fresh study.”

MILLER THE CHRISTIAN

The sea, and *The Cruise of the Betsey* also, however, served as a stage for Miller's theological discussions. It is worthwhile at this point to discuss

these before examining how the sea was used to express them; Miller's theology was of a surprisingly nuanced nature, at least from a modern perspective. Indeed, his views on palaeontology and the implications it posed for religion were more reconciled than might at first be expected. Miller was certainly a creationist, in the sense that he described the fossils he discovered during his time on the *Betsy* in terms of 'creations', or phases of creation on the part of God. He also assumed that humanity's presence on the Earth was simply another of these phases, meaning that the final creation would be in line with Biblical prophecy and so would be 'a better and a last creation coming, in which man shall re-appear, not to oppress and devour his fellow-men, and in which there shall be no such wrongs perpetrated as it is my present purpose to record . . .'.

For Miller, the natural beauty and symmetry he saw in the natural world, be it extinct or extant, was proof of a divine creator, his depictions of nature both scientific and poetic as discussed earlier.¹⁶

Yet comparisons between Miller and modern creationism, which is an ideological and political anti-science movement, are limited. Miller saw the creation of Earth and the emergence, extinction and development of life within an existing context of an ancient Earth and a non-literal reading of Biblical texts which was neither unusual nor radical for the times he was writing in.¹⁷ For Miller, the existence of geological periods such as the Carboniferous (approximately 358–299 MYA) and Devonian (419–358 MYA) were matters of fact, not contention, and his understanding of Geology and geological timeframes were on par with the scientific consensus at that time.¹⁸

If Miller was no Darwinian, he was no literalist either, and needs to be seen in terms of the existing scientific and religious contexts of the time. It is notable, for example, that he pointedly assured his readers that his writing was scientific rather than 'romantic', despite his own literary influences, and went so far as to say, in his 1857 book, *The Testimony of the Rocks*,¹⁹ that:

No blank chaotic gap of death and darkness separated the creation to which man belongs from that of the old extinct elephant, hippopotamus, and hyæna; for familiar animals such as the red deer, the roe, the fox, the wild cat, and the badger, lived throughout the period which connected their times with our own; and so I have

been compelled to hold, that the days of creation were not natural, but prophetic days, and stretched far back into the bygone eternity.

In so doing, Miller actively rejected the more literal reading of the Book of Genesis that he once subscribed to,²⁰ preferring instead to interpret the fossils he excavated within a mix of empiricism and theology as metaphor, in the process helping to popularise this reading of the Bible and geological empiricism.²¹

In other words, Miller fitted into an existing discourse whereby *Theology and Science* were seen as complimentary and where a 'Young Earth Hypothesis' was seen as wilfully absurd,²² an outlook which later clashed openly with Darwinian evolution but still existed within the mainstream discussions of the day. He was not unusual in this regard even amongst his fellow Free Church ministers. In *Rambles of a Geologist*²³ he goes into some detail discussing the Cretaceous period fossils in the collection of a friend – and Free Church minister – called Mr Longmuir, who Miller describes as:

[. . .] sedulously attentive to the proper duties of his office, but who has yet found time enough to render himself an accomplished geologist; and whose week-day lectures on the science attract crowds, who receive from them, in many instances, their first knowledge of the strange revolutions of which our globe has been the subject, blent with the teachings of a wholesome theology.

Indeed, Miller was one amongst many evangelical figures who were not threatened by geology so much as fascinated by it. He is best seen as part of the development of earth science than as a challenge to it, his Old Earth theology not the result of a challenge posed by geology but existing before its emergence as a modern science.²⁴ Indeed, Miller would openly attack the 'scriptural geologists' who cherry-picked scripture and evidence to support their reading of geological evidence,²⁵ and would even go so far as to muse as to whether God did indeed create life through 'a law of development' that continued to his day and beyond.²⁶ His was a strong faith, but not one removed from reason or science.

How then does this relate to the sea? As *The Cruise of the Betsey* demonstrates, the combination of a sea-going setting and fossilised sea beasts went

well with Miller's more spiritual musings. Importantly, the *Betsey* was itself a yacht owned and run by the Free Church – religion was not so much the theme of the book as the means through which it was enabled. Of course, it is also worth noting that Miller only uses the word 'God' fourteen times in his work, whereas the word 'fossil' or a variation of that word is used over one hundred times. Instead, Miller's religious preoccupations are manifested in the means of his seafaring, the *Betsey* itself.

As mentioned earlier, Miller compared the *Betsey* in flattering terms to 'a staunch Free Churchwoman' which is also a pun on his part given that ships were and continue to be gendered as female. Indeed, it is the idea of a church-owned ship that preoccupies the religious imagination of Miller more than the theological implications of fossils. For example, at one point, he discusses the loss of one sailor's sou'wester in flippant terms:

Should any conscientious mariner pick up anywhere in the Atlantic a serviceable ochre-coloured *sou-wester*, not at all the worse for the wear, I give him to wit that he holds Free Church property, and that he is heartily welcome to hold it, leaving it to himself to consider whether a benefaction to its full value, deducting salvage, is not owing, in honour, to the Sustenation Fund.

In many ways, the ecclesiastical nature of the ship is used as an excuse for whimsy on Miller's part. 'Hurrah for the Free Church yacht *Betsey*!' he says at one point, the yacht having navigated through a rough passage. Elsewhere he wryly observes that a hail of shot fired from the boat at a shoal of porpoises must 'have astonished the fat sleek fellows' on account of the gunfire coming from a 'Free Church Yacht'. Here the unusual nature of a ship owned by a church is used by Miller to satirise the more worldly aspects of his faith. His first encounter with the *Betsey*, after all, pokes fun at its bunting with 'the legend, "Free Church Yacht"' hung up in the state room next to Miller's own cabin. Then there is the farcical spectacle of a sheep that accidentally strangles itself on the deck, and the sight of 'two ragged boys' on a boat startled by the 'unexpected apparition of some one aboard the Free Church yacht' – Miller himself. They hide themselves in fear, having tried to avoid that evening's service on the nearby island.²⁷

This reflects an independence of mind and spirit that would not have gone down well with the more staid elements of the Free Church movement. A year after his voyage, in 1847, Miller would openly clash with the Free Church over the editorial independence of *The Witness* and its plans for education, which he saw as an attempt to shackle teaching to clerical agendas. Miller prevailed, but at the cost of good relations with his church, at least in private, until his death.²⁸ His fusing of romanticism in his theology, and his celebration of nature, also marked him apart from other Evangelicals who rejected the artistic as being too close to the Catholicism they rejected with some vigour.²⁹

Yet this coincides with an altogether more prosaic depiction of day-to-day religious life in the Inner Hebrides where the *Betsey* was also used as a means of transporting Free Church ministers to their island-bound flocks and for Miller to meet clerics both of this faith and others. The Free Church itself saw a golden opportunity to expand overseas in the colonies, and Miller's time on the *Betsey* was indicative of wider ambitions on the part of his church at the time.³⁰

Miller uses the *Betsey* and his journey by sea as a means of exploring a wide range of communities, including those where other faiths, such as Catholicism, are practised, and while he reserves his admiration for his own denomination, he does not hesitate to discuss the aftermath of the 1843 Disruption, where Church of Scotland clergy split off to form the Free Church³¹ and often had to compete with their old church and Catholicism for followers.

In that sense, Miller's choice of a sea voyage to explore the aftermath of the Disruption is appropriate. On the islands, he portrays a variety of fragmented, isolated religious communities who nonetheless prosper; whether this is due to selective observation on Miller's part, or due to the very real dynamism and enthusiasm that existed amongst the new church's congregation at that time³² is not so important as the metaphorical idea Miller is expressing. Here faith has not been weakened by fragmentation (be it political, theological or geographical) but has prospered, the *Betsey* serving as the literal and symbolic means through which this new church sustains and develops itself. While Miller pokes fun at the idea of a 'Free Church' yacht, it nonetheless represents the means through which his faith is maintained and nurtured. As one Free Church Minister is quoted by Miller as saying:

[. . .] I suggested to them the scheme of the *Betsey*, as the only scheme through which I could keep up unbroken my connection with my people. So the trial is now over, and here we are, and yonder is the *Betsey*.'

Again, the sea acquires importance as a stage for Miller's ideas. As he also observes, 'my friend preached two long energetic discourses, and then returned to the yacht, "a worn and weary man."' The use of a ship in Christian metaphor was, of course, long established. Early Christians referred to the ship both as a way to complete one's journey through life, with the final destination dictated by one's decisions beforehand, and as a means of salvation. Allusions to Noah's Ark were not uncommon, while the parallels between the shape of a ship's mast and the cross were often made clear, to the point that ships became a symbol of faith for many Christians from late Antiquity onwards.³³

Miller was, therefore, quite deliberately using the *Betsey* as a metaphor for his ideas and also as a way of associating the still-new Free Church with a longstanding Christian tradition, establishing its legitimacy in the process. Miller also makes a point of observing the personal cost that many Free Church ministers had to face as a result of the Disruption – one minister is quoted as saying he had to sell all the livestock on his *glebe* to support himself after he split with the established church – the image of the *Betsey* surviving on its journey through stormy seas being a fitting allegory for the political argument Miller makes in the favour of the Free Church.

In other words, Miller's sea voyage reflected a writer who was comfortable with his faith and yet also willing to explore it and how it related to the wider world. Written only three years after the creation of his denomination, for Miller the aftermath of the Disruption was more controversial than the age of the Earth or the taxonomy of fossils, and the sea was the means through which he could undertake this journey.

MILLER THE SOCIAL CAMPAIGNER

Another theme covered in detail by *Cruise of the Betsey* concerns the social conditions Hugh Miller encountered on his sea journey. Again, the geography and nature of these island communities was influenced by the sea

and Miller explores this fully in his narrative. One example of this was his description of the island of Rum:

All was solitary. We could see among the deserted fields the grass-grown foundations of cottages razed to the ground; but the valley, more desolate than that which we had left, had not even its single inhabited dwelling: it seemed as if man had done with it forever. The island, eighteen years before, had been divested of its inhabitants, amounting at the time to rather more than four hundred souls, to make way for one sheep-farmer and eight thousand sheep.

Miller was an avowed critic of the Highland Clearances,³⁴ and his choice of Rum to elaborate his views was quite deliberate. The isolation of the island and the ease of how it was so quickly depopulated provided an ideal metaphor for Miller's argument, the desolation of Rum being in effect a microcosm for the greater depopulations and uprooting of communities on the Scottish mainland. In many ways, then, Miller chose an interesting time to commence his journey. Five years before, in 1841, a process had begun whereby the population of the Inner Hebrides underwent a steady decline for the next seventy years, until they had almost halved by 1911.³⁵ Miller quite deliberately observed the irony of the island beginning as and then finally becoming once more a wild and unsettled area. The human farmers and shepherds who settled the island in-between had been cast out in favour of the then-current owner, 'some wealthy Englishman', turning it into a deer-forest. 'Once more, a strange and surely most melancholy cycle!' Miller concludes, the separation of the island by the sea enabling its desolation at the hands of a larger movement sweeping Scotland as a whole.

The island setting of Miller's record enabled him to make further comment in other ways. When threatened by the owner of the Scur of Eigg, an escarpment containing many fossil deposits, Miller uses the opportunity to ridicule him – an absentee doctor who resided in Aberdeen – by wondering, sarcastically, if his fossil-hunting makes him a kind of poacher. He extends this further to make a broader political point and condemnation of the land-owning class that was causing such harm to the islanders:

If I be cast and committed, – I, who have poached over only a few miserable districts in Scotland, – pray, what will become of some of them, – the Lyells, Bucklands, Murchisons and Sedgwicks, – who have poached over whole continents?

Again, Miller uses the islands of the Inner Hebrides as microcosms of a broader system of change across Scotland, where crofters and other established communities were evicted from their smallholdings in favour of game estates, sheep raising and recreation for the landowning classes.³⁶ This was doubly of interest to Miller as the clearances also lead to a revival in Presbyterianism as a reaction to the instability of the time and so a potential new flock for the Free Church.³⁷ Certainly, this was reflected in some parts of the Inner Hebrides, where up to nine out of ten inhabitants were members of the Free Church, to the point that it did not, in fact, have enough ministers to go round in the wake of the Disruption.³⁸

Miller's main area of interest, however, was the suffering of the islanders themselves. At one point, Miller accompanies a minister in a visit to a chronically ill woman, 'who had been bed-ridden for ten years'. Impoverished by her husband's own ill-health and the loss of her two sons, both of whom – Miller note, significantly – were sailors who died at sea, the parishioner lived in a turf and stone hovel in appalling conditions. Miller describes her in piteous terms, deliberately dehumanising her as a means of emphasising the utter destitution of her condition and the blighted surroundings she was surrounded by, yet hinting at lost dignity and a life beyond poverty and suffering:

The little hole in the wall had formed the poor creature's only communication with the face of the external world for ten weary years. She lay under a dingy coverlet, which, whatever its original hue, had come to differ nothing in colour from the graveyard earth, which must so soon better supply its place. What perhaps first struck the eye was the strange flatness of the bed-clothes, considering that a human body lay below: there seemed scarce bulk enough under them for a human skeleton. The light of the opening fell on the corpse-like features of the woman, – sallow, sharp, bearing at once the stamp of disease and of famine; and yet it was evident, notwithstanding, that they had once been agreeable [. . .]

Miller uses this as a preamble to his final polemic, a condemnation of the Poor Law which prevented paupers from seeking redress directly through the courts. While praising the family's neighbours who supplied what help they could, 'though they had little to spare', Miller also attacks both the landowner and the local parish for refusing to assist as well as the legislation that allowed them to do this. Sarcastically, he says of the English politicians who voted for the Law's assent that they were doubtless 'humane men, friendly to an equal-handed justice', yet he is only too aware that this case '[. . .] is but one of many which the Island of Eigg will be found to furnish'.

The sea, however, plays a significant role in this scene also; Miller notes that the hovel's 'window' (in effect, a literal hole in the wall) allows 'a downward peep of sea and shore' and he reminds the reader that the proximity of the sea, that destructive force which surrounded them, seemed to go hand in hand with desolation and horror. Yet it also brought the means of salvation, of a spiritual if not physical sort, in the form of the *Betsey* and the ministers it ferried. Again, the sea is used to suggest isolation not just of a physical but a social nature, where the poor are cut off socially as well as geographically, yet also a means of bringing spiritual renewal.

While social conditions were not, at least officially, the main aim of Miller's writing *The Cruise of the Betsey* or *Rambles of a Geologist*, he still used every opportunity to present and critique them, and enlist the sea toward this goal. In *Rambles* . . ., upon meeting one 'cadaverously pale and miserable-looking' old woman, he uses the encounter to launch another attack on the Poor Law:

The old woman [. . .] was I doubt not, one of our ill-provided Highland paupers, that starve under a law which, while it has dried up the genial streams of voluntary charity in the country and presses hard upon the means of the humbler classes, alleviates little, if at all, the sufferings of the extreme poor.

Miller again chooses his examples carefully. His meeting with the old pauper takes place on the banks of the Auldgrande River, or the Allt Graad, or River Glass, as it is now known today. In its original Scots Gaelic, Allt Graad was *Allt Grànnda* which means 'ugly stream', while the word 'grande' itself – or rather, 'granderie' – has connotations of witchcraft

and the occult in Orkney Scots.³⁹ The river itself flows into the Firth of Cromarty and so is employed by Miller to suggest an inevitable descent into a sinister sea and the despair contained within.

Miller's rich imagery uses horror and a dark manifestation of nature – particularly water and the sea – to make his political case. This was quite deliberate on his part. For Miller, the oceans were all too often abysses threatening to consume their victims, and there was not always a good Christian ship there to provide rescue or succour. For Miller, faith was important, but so too was social justice.

CONCLUSIONS

The Cruise of the Betsey therefore succinctly summarises both Hugh Miller and his many facets. Here we also see the deep nuanced fascination he felt for the sea, and his willingness to explore these conflicted, often dark thoughts through his work and as a means of expressing it. To say Miller was haunted by the sea is certainly true, but equally true was the fact that he used it to define himself and derive the inspiration through which a remarkable life realised much of its potential.

Notes

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- 4 Bayne, p. 454.
- 5 Samuel Taylor Coleridge, *The Rime of the Ancient Mariner*, www.poetryfoundation.org/poem/173253 [accessed 20 October 2014].
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- 26 David W. Bebbington, 'Science and Evangelical Theory in Britain from Wesley to Orr', in *Evangelicals and Science in Historical Perspective*, ed. by David N. Livingstone, D. G. Hart and Mark A. Noll (Oxford, Oxford University Press), p. 131.

- 27 Another example of Miller's whimsical sense of humour was in an 1852 letter to his wife, where he mentions his two-year-old son: '[. . .] Poor little Hugh, who is, I suspect, not intelligent enough to feel any interest in papa's adventures, must be regarded as that ignorant, but not uncared-for portion of the community which education has not yet reached.' Hugh Miller Junior would subsequently follow in his father's footsteps and become a geologist for the Ordnance Geological Survey.
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